

Synthesis and Characterization Zirconia added Glass-Ceramics

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.15266616

Abstract:

Glass samples were prepared by conventional melt quenching technique. Glasses were converted to glass-ceramics by choosing two stage heat treatment. The density of the glass and glass-ceramic samples was found to increase with ZrO₂ addition. Dielectric properties of glass and glass-ceramic samples have been studied. Ferroelectric measurement was also been for these samples. The dielectric & ferroelectric properties were improved with ZrO₂ addition.

Keywords: Glass; Two Stage Heat Treatment; Glass-ceramics

Introduction:

Lead titanate is a perovskite-type ferroelectric material with high Curie temperature of 490 °C which make them attractive for high-temperature and high-frequency piezoelectric applications. However, pure lead titanate ceramics are very difficult to be sintered because of its large lattice anisotropy. PbTiO₃ ceramics when prepared by conventional route generally have microcracks and fracture on cooling below T_c as a result of the large spontaneous strain generated when the structure changes from cubic to tetragonal. This has restricted the applications of undoped PT ceramics. The glass-ceramic route is promising way of fabricating Lead Titanate [1,4].

But the effect of ZrO₂ addition on the dielectric and ferroelectric properties has not been fully explored in lead titanate-based glass-ceramics.

Experimental:

Glasses with composition 25PbO: 25TiO₂ : (25-X) ZrO₂ : (25+X) B₂O₃ (where

X= 0, 2.5, 5, 7.5 and 10 mol %) were prepared in the temperature range 1200 to 1300 °C. For crystallization process, the glass samples were given two stage heat treatment at 495 °C and 595 °C. All the glass samples were heat treated for 32 hours. The density of glass and glass-ceramics was measured by Archimedes principle. The dielectric constant of samples was measured as a function of temperature using dielectric analyser. The ferroelectric hysteresis study of the glass ceramic samples has been done.

Results and Discussion:

The density values for glass-ceramic samples are observed to be higher than those of corresponding glasses and increase with ZrO₂ addition. The values of room temperature dielectric constant for glass and glass-ceramic samples are observed to increase with ZrO₂ addition as given in the table 1. This may be attributed to rigidity of structure which is in good correlation with the observed density variation.

Table1

X (mol %)	ρ_{glass} (g/cm ³)	$\rho_{\text{glass-ceramic}}$ (g/cm ³)	$\epsilon_{\text{RT glass}}$	$\epsilon_{\text{RT glass-ceramic}}$	Volume fraction of PbTiO ₃
0	4.86	4.95	36	70	36.58
2.5	4.91	4.97	44	82	44.78
5	5.03	5.27	42	84	56.07
7.5	5.13	5.22	45	98	56.34
10	5.21	5.49	67	100	56.89

The volume fraction of tetragonal lead titanate phase precipitate in the glass-ceramic samples is calculated from XRD patterns by comparison of integral intensities from X-ray diffraction patterns of amorphous and completely crystalline samples as per the method [5].

The values of volume fraction of lead titanate phase are tabulated in Table. It is observed that the volume fraction of lead titanate phase is increased with the ZrO₂ addition. The observed room temperature dielectric constant shows good correlation with the volume fraction of lead titanate.

Fig. 1. Ferroelectric hysteresis loop for 2.5 mol % glass-ceramic sample.

The P-E measurement is carried out at room temperature. A representative hysteresis loops for glass-ceramic samples 2.5 mol % is shown in Fig. 1. The non saturated loop observed for these glass-ceramic samples are may be due to the presence of residual glass phase [6].

Conclusion:

From the above study it can be concluded that the density, dielectric constant and ferroelectric properties are improved due to addition of ZrO₂ in the lead titanate glass-ceramics. These glass-ceramic samples may be further explored for device applications.

References:

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